

Managing Work Place Motivation

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Abstract

Employee motivation is essentially about commitment to doing something. In the context of a business, motivation can be said to be about “The will to work”. Motivation is an internal drive that activates behavior and gives its direction. The word motivation is coined from the Latin word “movere”, which means to move. The term motivation theory is concerned with the process that describes why and how human behavior is activated and detected. It is regarded as one of the most important areas of the study in the field of organizational behavior. Every organization needs to have well motivation in employees to perform their work good in the organization when the employee feel good their jobs, certain factors tend to consistently related to job satisfaction the comfortableness of an employee in the organization. My study is to examine the various factors of motivation in employee with reference to know the level of motivation in employee of the company and to provide practical suggestions for the improvement of organization's performance. Employees are the heart of any organization. For any organization to operate smoothly and without any interruption, employee of an organization not only has a good relationship with the top management, but also, they maintain a healthy and professional relationship with their co-workers. The following study is a self-conducted research on how motivational tools impact the performance of employee for betterment. The study also focused on de-motivation factors affecting employee performance negatively. A sample of individuals was selected and was interviewed with self-administrated to obtain indicate that if employee are positively motivated, it improves both their effectiveness and efficiency drastically for achieving organizational goals.

Introduction

In an organization, management tries to coordinate various factors of production in such a way that each factor contributes to its maximum efficiency to achieve organizational goals. So far as non-human factors, i.e., materials, machines, etc., are concerned, their efficiency depends largely upon the type of technology being followed by the performance level of human factors who handle and control these non-human factors. To make total factors efficient and effective, one has to improve the performance is determined by two factors.

- Level of ability to do certain work
- Level of motivation.

These two factors are to be multiplied rather than added. This can be expressed as:

$$\text{Performance} = \text{Ability} \times \text{Motivation}$$

Thus, performance level would the high if both these are high. If a worker is very capable of doing certain things but they are

otherwise not willing to do the work, his performance level would not be high. While ability to do is governed by education and training, willingness to do can be effected by the factors governing human behavior in the organization.

Meaning

Motivation is an important factors which encourages persons to give their best performance and helps in reaching enterprise goals. A strong positive motivation will enable the increased motivation will reduce their performance. A key element in personnel management is motivation.

According to Likert, “It is the core of management which shows that every human being gives him a sense of worth in face-to face groups which are most important to the employee. A supervisor should strive to treat individuals with dignity and recognition of their personal worth”.

Nature of Motivation

Motivation is a psychological phenomenon which generates within an individual. A person feels the lack of certain needs, to satisfy which he feels working more. The need satisfying ego motivates a person to do better than they normally do.

- Motivation is an inner felling which energizes a person to work more.
- The emotions or desires of a person prompt him for doing a particular work.
- There are unsatisfied needs of a person which disturb his equilibrium.
- A person moves to fulfill his unsatisfied needs by conditioning his energies.
- There are dormant energies in a person which are activated by channelizing them into actions.

Importance of motivation

Motivation is one of the most important factors determining organizational efficiency. All organizational facilities will go waste in the lack of motivated people to utilize these facilities effectively. Every superior in the organization must motivate his subordinates for the right types of behavior.

Diagnosing human behavior and analyzing as to why people behave in a particular way is of prime importance in motivating them irrespective of the nature of the organization because individual in the basic component of any organization. The importance of motivation is an organization may be summed up as follows:

1. High performance Level. Motivated employees put higher performance as compared to other employees. In a study by William James, it was found that motivated employees worked at close to 80-90 per cent of their ability.

2. Low employee Turnover and Absenteeism. Motivated employees stay in the organization and their absenteeism is quite low. High turnover and absenteeism create many problems in the organization.

3. Acceptance of Organizational Changes. Organizations are created in the society. Because of changes in the society changes in technology, value system, etc, organization has to incorporate those changes to cope up with the requirement of the time.

Motivation and Behaviour

Motivation causes goal-directed behavior. Feeling of a need by a person causes him to behave in such a way that he tries to satisfy himself so that he does not feel the lack of that particular thing.

A need, that is, the feeling that something is required, creates tension in mind and transforms itself into want depending upon environment. This tension is released when this particular need is satisfied by certain behavior again in environment that is.

Incentives exist to satisfy the needs. Behavior ends the moment tension is released. However, satisfaction of one need leads to feeling to another either of different need or the same need after lapse of certain time.

1. Flight: One way of handling a frustration is to leave the field or withdraw from the scene. Employees quit jobs that prove to be frustrating.

2. Apathy: Another method of withdrawal is showing indifference. If an employee does not leave frustration jobs physically, he may remain absent psychologically, that is reading on the job, daydreaming, thinking of almost anything except the work at hand, etc..,

3. Aggression: A more common reaction to frustration is aggression, an act against someone or something. An employee being denied a promotion may become aggressive and verbally berate his superior.

Contingency Approach of Motivation

The appraisal of various theories of motivation and result as how a manager can be sure about the way he can motivate people in the organization. The various theories suggest that there is in universal device applicable to everyone. It is not possible to motivate in single method. Thus universality of motivational strategy is out of question. Following factors seem to be important in this respect:

Individual personality: Individual difference suggests that all people do not like the same things. Consequently, their need pattern will be different.

Organizational climate: It means many individual's needs are modified by organizational factors. The various organizational factors may be termed as organizational climate which will be discussed later.

Available incentives: organizational climate will affect human behavior, what is more important for motivating people is the availability of various types of incentives through which they can be motivated.

Job Enrichment

Policy on incentive must maintain a high level of flexibility. It must be prepared to adjust incentives to the man, the time, and situation. Incentives should be used as the means of offering satisfaction to the whole man. Job enrichment may be an important practice in meeting 'whole man' needs. It represents a new, popular non-monetary motivational technique. It is an extension of job enlargement technique. The difference between job enrichment and job enlargement lies

on the nature of additions to the job. Enlargement involves a horizontal loading. Or expansion, of the adding of more tasks of the same general nature of type. Enrichment involves vertical loading addition giving more challenge. Thus job enrichment applies to improvement of job in such a way that it has more motivators than before and at the same time maintaining the degree of maintenance factors. It is based on the assumption that in order to motivate personnel. The job itself must provide opportunities for achievement, recognition, responsibility, advancement and growth.

Incentives

The needs of individuals serve as driving forces in human behavior. In the context of these needs, managements try to govern the behavior of employees in satisfying their needs. The objects which are perceived to satisfy their needs are called incentives. Incentives may be either positive or negative. Positive incentives attract people and when they obtain these incentives they feel satisfied. **Examples of positive incentives** are increase in pay, prospect of promotion, etc., employees will try to achieve these. **Negative incentives**, are those which motivate an individual to abstain from doing something.

Individuals have varied types of needs. Some of them can be satisfied by money, while others cannot be satisfied by money alone. On the basis of this, the various incentives which may be used by the organizations may be classified into two parts, viz., financial incentives and non-financial incentives. Different financial and non-financial incentives have been shown in the charts on the following page.

Rewards

Reward as motivators divides employee motivation into two categories, **Intrinsic and Extrinsic motivation**. Intrinsic rewards are internal, psychological rewards such as a sense of accomplishment or doing something because it makes one feel good. Extrinsic rewards are rewards that other people give to you as a money, compliments, bonuses, or trophies. This applies to Douglas McGregor's scientific Theory that formed theory X, which applies to the extrinsic wants of employees. The basis for the motivation is supervision structure and money. Scientific theory based on the grounds that employees don't want to work so they have to be forced to do their job, and enticed with monetary compensation. Theory Y, also derived from Mc Gregor's theory, says that employees are motivated different factors can be used to heighten the intrinsic benefit that employee are receiving at their job".

Conclusion

Regardless of age and gender, respondents in this research seem to have a common interest or goal. This I believe may have some practical implications for organizations, but perhaps its provision and implications may not be as difficult because employees seem to have similar preference and wants. That is, they want their work to be as satisfying as it could be. Generally, respondents in this research place high emphasis on job satisfaction and other factors, which that are largely of basic in nature. Therefore organizations that may

provide such enabling environments facilitate and tirelessly promote these need factors could attract and retain high caliber employees Harpaz argues that when work is “interesting and challenging, people are inspired to perform more than is obligated to warrant their instrumental attainments”, In other words. Employees may put additional effort with the hope of reaching their potential and **accomplishing worthwhile ends**.

References

Gupta, CB. “Ex-head”, Department of Commerce University of Delhi.

Srinivasan, NP. “Formally Head of the Department of Commerce University of Madras”.

Prasad, LM. “Department of Business Management Pruvanihal university”, Jaunpur (UP)